

EU-Funded FIC-FIGHTERS Project Aims to Turn Waste into Sustainable Products

Seville, Spain – 9 September 2024 - The FIC-FIGHTERS project is a groundbreaking research project dedicated to developing sustainable waste management practices. The project aims to transform phosphogypsum (PG) waste and other industrial by-products into valuable raw materials for various industries, including paper, cement, batteries, fertilisers, and detergents.

Over a 48-month period, FIC-FIGHTERS will engage local actors, industries, authorities, SMEs, research and technology development centres, and universities to implement scalable waste recovery processes reaching Technology Readiness Levels (TRL) 6-7. The initiative focuses on developing circular economic models that prioritise the valorisation of waste materials and reduce environmental impact.

FIC-FIGHTERS is a local democracy initiative bringing together 25 partners and 1 associated partner from 11 European countries, including SMEs, universities, private and public research organisations, large companies, not-for-profit associations, and government authorities. Supported by the Circular Cities and Regions Initiative (CCRI) and engaging diverse stakeholders, FIC-FIGHTERS aims to pioneer new standards in waste recovery and urban development.

Funded under the EU's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, the FIC-FIGHTERS project supports the European Green Deal by demonstrating large-scale circular and systemic solutions for regenerating seven local phosphogypsum stacks in Europe. The project aims to create new business opportunities, reduce greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and promote climate-neutral practices among citizens. It will engage a diverse group of stakeholders, including local communities, industries, NGOs, and government bodies, to build sustainable urban environments and create jobs, contributing to economic recovery following recent global challenges.

By employing innovative chemical routes and capturing industrial CO₂, FIC-FIGHTERS will produce high-value commercial products while reducing the carbon footprint associated with traditional waste management practices. The project's comprehensive approach will enhance knowledge transfer across European cities and regions, facilitate replication and scalability of systemic solutions, and ultimately accelerate the transition towards sustainable and resilient urban ecosystems.

For more information, please visit fic-fighters.eu.

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About FIC-FIGHTERS

The FIC-FIGHTERS project is a groundbreaking initiative focused on advancing sustainable waste management solutions across Europe. By converting phosphogypsum waste into useful materials, the project supports the EU's Green Deal objectives and promotes sustainable urban development practices. Through innovative technologies and stakeholder collaboration, FIC-FIGHTERS aims to set a benchmark in circular economy practices.

Disclaimer

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